

The Ripple Effects Toolkit **How local actors can drive change from the *in-between***

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Executive summary

Across Europe, many initiatives are working to drive green transitions, not only at the level of individuals or systems, but in the spaces in between. These ‘*in-between*’ spaces (often referred to as the *meso* in research) are where local action connects people, organisations, and structures, enabling change to emerge and spread.

Drawing on insights from the [SHARED GREEN DEAL](#) 24 social experiments, as well as contributions from over 100 participants in a series of six online workshops, this toolkit responds to a clear need: to make this sometimes less visible work in the *meso* more visible, understandable, and recognised. It aims to legitimise and strengthen efforts that operate in these *in-between* spaces by translating abstract academic concepts into practical, accessible tools, while enabling users to identify, amplify, and navigate the ripple effects of their actions.

This toolkit is designed for anyone working with communities and collective action towards sustainability, whether local citizen initiatives, civil society organisations, municipalities, practitioners, facilitators, or researchers. It supports those who bring together diverse actors, navigate complexity, and seek to create meaningful change across different levels.

The toolkit first introduces the concept of the *in-between* and illustrates how it has been applied in the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments. It then invites readers to move into practice through **three flexible exercises for action and reflection**. These exercises help users map their initiative, explore connections and ‘bridges’ across the *in-between*, and identify potential ripple effects of their work.

The toolkit can be used individually or collectively, for example within a team, a project partnership, or a group of stakeholders. The exercises are adaptable to different contexts, formats, and timeframes: they can be used independently, combined, or explored sequentially, depending on your needs. Each exercise can take between 10 and 40 minutes.

By working with this toolkit, users can gain new perspectives on their initiatives, uncover hidden dynamics, and better understand how their actions can influence both people and systems. Ultimately, it seeks to support more intentional, connected, and impactful pathways towards behavioural, social, and cultural change.

“

The best that designers of lives and institutions can do is to create contexts that, as experience and thought show, make certain activities very or more likely.’

(Schatzki 2012, p.22)

The team

The team consists of the authors and contributing partners, which form a group of 10 consortium partners (of a total of 22) from the SHARED GREEN DEAL project and who are also founding members of the Shared Green Societies.

The contributing partners supported the toolkit development process and the preliminary testing stage, consisting of a series of six online workshops in various European languages that were held during March and April 2026.

in alphabetical order by surname

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1. Introduction

The starting point

This toolkit was inspired by research into how local actors can drive change. Based on the social experiments of the SHARED GREEN DEAL project¹, we explored how these initiatives drove local change by bringing together stakeholders in new and novel forms of engagement, while connecting such learning processes to broader organisational and systemic contexts. We understand these social experiments as examples of experimenting with and in what we call the *in-between* spaces - in academic terms referred to as the *meso* (Foulds et al. 2025a) - as the space between individuals and larger systems. Existing approaches to social change have tended to focus either on individuals and their behaviours ('micro' perspectives) or on broader systems and structures ('macro' perspectives). However, this dualism can overlook the relational and intermediary processes through which change emerges across scales and contexts. This toolkit responds to that gap by offering a *meso* perspective for understanding and engaging with these *in-between* spaces. We approach this work through action research because we have been actively involved and learning ourselves throughout.

Main aim

The aim of this toolkit is to support people working in the *in-between*, to specifically help strengthen sustainability initiatives. In particular, we hope to aid reflections on potential ripple effects of these initiatives. We believe it is important to strengthen this type of work carried out in the *in-between* spaces (i.e. the *meso* in research terms), where local action connects individuals and systems, to give enhanced visibility and understanding to the dynamics in the *in-between*. We hope this will support the cultivation of collective actions and their relevance for impacting both the individuals and systems in which the sustainability initiatives are embedded.

This toolkit will help to translate some of our learnings and wishes to offer practitioners, and all interested change-makers inspiration on how to integrate or enhance their work by taking an '*in-between perspective*'. We believe this toolkit has the potential to strengthen intervention strategies, making them more impactful in promoting and implementing change.

Target audience

This toolkit is directed at any person or organisation (e.g. local citizen initiatives, Civil Society Organisations and local associations, but also municipality-led initiatives) working across a range of community settings and groups that engage different actors in their fields to drive change towards green transitions.

What we learned about creating change

Through SHARED GREEN DEAL, we found that lasting change often grows from the connections that emerge from these spaces *in between* where people, organisations, and wider structures meet. When community action departs from these *in-between* spaces, it can create ripple effects that more effectively connect everyday action with wider organisational and policy change.

1 SHARED GREEN DEAL is an EU Horizon2020-funded project, exploring how behavioural, social and cultural change can support the transition towards more sustainable societies, in line with the EU Green Deal. Through 24 social experiments across Europe, SHARED GREEN DEAL worked with local actors to test how such change can emerge in practice. Central to these experiments was this concept of the *inbetweenness* (i.e. meso thinking). More information on the project in general can be found: www.sharedgreendeal.eu or <https://doi.org/10.3030/101036640>.

Our toolkit development process

Led by scholars from the Institute of Social Sciences from University of Lisbon (ICS ULisboa), this toolkit was developed iteratively within a task-specific working group. We delved into different toolkit formats and discussed different approaches that were then integrated into an internal facilitators' training on the *in-between*. As part of this process, we designed and conducted a series of online workshops to test our ideas with participants from Northern, Southern, Western, and Eastern Europe. During March and April 2026, these workshops were held in Portuguese, German, English, Slovenian, and Spanish, to test how our preliminary toolkit ideas resonated with a variety of practitioners active in the larger sustainability transformation field. In total, 124 participants from 17 different countries joined the workshops. Two of the exercises included in this toolkit were tested in these workshops, using Miro as an online platform for collaborative exchange.

We analysed automatically generated anonymised workshop transcripts, as well as contributions on the Miro boards and evaluative feedback collected via Mentimeter. Participants' feedback helped us make necessary adjustments and further refine our approach.

An important piece of feedback from participants on the potential usefulness of such a toolkit was that it would give visibility and legitimisation to the manifold initiatives already happening in the *in-between*. Another key insight was the value of a toolkit that helps practitioners reflect on their current intervention strategies and assess whether they need to be better aligned with the challenges they face.

The insights gained through this process are reflected in the final version of this toolkit.

Suggestions for readers when engaging with this toolkit

In this toolkit, we invite you to engage with reflective practices about your initiative(s) that may lead to insights related to the place and people where your work is embedded. The depths and perspective change can vary in accordance with time, (mental) availability and motivation to engage in the exercises of this toolkit. We do not offer a step-by-step guide on how to carry out social experiments or any type of 'meso-initiatives', but we offer guided exercises to learn more about the *in-between* and to explore how your work may create ripple effects spreading out from such an *in-between space*. These exercises may help you to better calibrate strategies and make your intervention more impactful and meaningful.

We encourage you not to expect universal solutions or guarantees of scalable outputs and outcomes; instead, bring an open and curious mind to gain new insights and ideas that may strengthen your work, contributing to more sustainable futures and a collectively shared European Green Deal.

2. Working with this toolkit

Who is this toolkit for?

This toolkit is designed for people who work **in and across the in-between** where local action connects to wider systems.

It is particularly relevant for:

- **Community organisations and initiatives** (e.g. NGOs, local businesses) working on sustainability and social innovation
- **Local and regional authorities** (e.g. municipalities) engaging with communities, pilots, or participatory processes
- **Practitioners and facilitators** involved in experimentation, co-creation, or living lab-type approaches
- **Educators, intermediaries, and community workers** supporting collective learning and change
- **Researchers and project partners** working closely with practice and policy

Many people already work in these *in-between spaces* (an observation confirmed during the six online workshops to test this toolkit) without necessarily naming themselves as such. This toolkit offers language, concepts, and practical reflections to **make their work more visible, intentional, and oriented towards ripple effects to support their efforts.**

How is this toolkit meant to be used?

This toolkit can be used individually or collectively, for example by a team of an initiative, or by a group of actors linked to a common purpose. Section 3 and 4 provide some background on our conceptual lens and concrete examples from the SHARED GREEN DEAL respectively. In Section 5, we present practical exercises that are flexible and can be adapted to multiple settings, formats and lengths.

It is possible to start with one exercise and do others on another day, or even potentially to do them all in a row, in one specific time window. Each exercise takes at least 10 minutes (likely maximum of 40 minutes), depending on the circumstances.

For group settings, e.g. a team meeting or a multi-actor workshop, we suggest to plan for at least 90 minutes (and ideally 2 hours) to ensure sufficient time for debriefing and exchange. See also the practical tips in Box 2.1.

Box 2.1. How to use the exercises in Section 5 - practical tips

We recommend, as a first step, to explore Section 3 and 4 to get familiarised with the in-between perspective.

When done individually

- Pick a quiet spot where you know you will be undisturbed for the time you reserved.
- Consider taking the toolkit to the outdoors, e.g. combine a walk with reaching a nice spot in nature where you can reflect and write.
- Take only the essentials - the toolkit, pen and paper and a water bottle, and anything else that supports you in getting to deeper thinking and reflecting.

When done in groups

- Make sure everyone is aware of the objective of the meeting to use this toolkit. Ideally share the toolkit before and suggest to read our understanding of the *in-between*, and to explore some of the interactive links (Sections 3 and 4).
- Meet in a convenient and appropriate spot that gives you privacy and undisturbed time. Ideally, you have the space to sit and to move.
- Consider meeting outdoors, when feasible, where you can connect to and sense nature.
- When involving a variety of actors, we recommend having a pre-designed facilitator or moderator to guide through the meeting.
- Ideally, 3-6 persons are in one group. Create as many groups as necessary.
- Consider, if having a pre-designed group moderator (in each group) could be useful.
- Include a plenary discussion at the end of the exercises. Consider whether having a rapporteur from each group might help getting impressions from each group in an effective way. This is context-dependent and can be adapted to specific needs.

3. What do we mean by the *in-between*?

There are different ways to approach behavioural, social and cultural change. Social Sciences and Humanities research on green transitions has thus far mostly focused on changes to either individual experiences ('micro') or structures ('macro'). This can mean that sometimes interventions focus on **individuals**, aiming to influence behaviour, awareness, or personal choices. At other times, they focus on **systems**, such as policies, infrastructures, funding models, or regulations. When we refer to the *in-between* (or the **meso**), we mean the spaces where **connections are actively made and negotiated**: between individuals and institutions, between everyday practices and formal systems, and between ideas and action (Rasmusen et al. 2019; Reid et al 2010; Schenk et al. 2007) (Fig. 3.1).

Fig. 3.1. Understanding the 'in-between' embedded between 'individuals' and 'systems'

These spaces are neither purely individual nor fully systemic. Rather than being a fixed 'middle level', they actively shape how change happens. Emerging from interactions between people, organisations, and wider structures, they influence how both everyday actions and larger systems evolve over time.

Box 3.1. Approaches to change: The *in-between* in a nutshell

In a simple form, approaches to behavioural, social and cultural change often consider two main levels:

The **systems level** includes broader structures such as political, economic, legal, and social systems. These shape the conditions in which we act and have developed over time.

*Illustrative example: A European directive on single-use plastics operates at the **systems level**, setting binding rules across countries.*

The **individuals level** focuses on people, their behaviours, attitudes, perceptions, and everyday decisions.

*Illustrative example: A municipality launching a website with energy-saving tips mainly targets **individual behaviour**.*

The **in-between** connects these two levels. It includes the spaces, relationships, and arrangements through which individual actions and system level structures interact and influence each other.

*Illustrative example: A **regional producers' association** reorganising how food is supplied to canteens and retailers is working in the *in-between*. By coordinating its members and prioritising seasonal and local products, it creates **new shared practices** that can influence both everyday behaviour and broader systems.*

Fig. 3.2. Illustrative examples of initiatives in the individuals - in-between - systems fields

Moving beyond ‘micro’ and ‘macro’

As said above, approaches focusing on the **micro level** tend to look at individuals: their attitudes, choices, knowledge, or behaviour. Such approaches often assume that change happens when individuals make different decisions, when having ‘sufficiently’ increased awareness and education, loading pressure onto the individual and less on systems structures and associated tensions.

Approaches focusing on the **macro level** tend to look at systems: policies, infrastructures, markets, or institutions. These approaches can overlook how such systems are interpreted, negotiated, and enacted in everyday life.

The *in-between spaces* matter because they are where these two levels meet and interact.

They are concerned with:

- How shared meanings are formed
- How practices become stabilised or disrupted
- How ideas travel between local action and formal governance

The Ripple Effects Toolkit focuses on this middle ground because transformation happens not just from the top down or the bottom up, but through the connections and feedback loops that link them. Learn more about the SHARED GREEN DEAL and its social experiments as examples for working in the *in-between* in Section 4.

Box 3.2. Why the *in-between* matters?

Understanding the *in-between* by considering a simple decision: taking the bus instead of driving

At the individual level, this practice involves personal priorities, habits, and values. But no amount of individual willpower can create change if the infrastructure is not there to enable adopting this practice: reliable buses, sensible timetables, routes that connect to where people actually live.

At the systems level, governments and institutions shape how public transport is funded, planned, and perceived by society. Yet even the best-designed systems falter without people willing to use them.

The meso level sits between these two. It is the space where individual choices and systemic structures interact, where community norms form, where local organizations operate, and where collective action takes shape. This is the *in-between* where local actors can bridge personal decisions and large-scale system change.

Watch the video [here](#) or scan the Qr

4. Working in the *in-between*: examples from the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments

In SHARED GREEN DEAL, social experiments were designed as **learning-by-doing processes** that are characterised by governing and engaging with multiple actors and remain open to learning by failure.

They create interactive spaces where people from different backgrounds can:

- share perspectives and experiences
- try out new ways of working and living
- reflect on what helps or holds back change

These experiments make it possible to explore new ideas, practices, and values while building relationships between different groups. They often connect people and organisations that do not usually work together, linking everyday actions with broader systems and debates.

In this set of examples, you can hear directly from SHARED GREEN DEAL local partners as they share their experiences.

Watch the playlist
Local Actions for a SHARED GREEN DEAL
[here](#) or scan the Qr

To help make sense of how these experiments work, we use six key perspectives – we call them ‘bridges’ as they are connectors between individuals and systems. Each bridge is framed as a guiding question (Figure 4.1):

Community visions:

How do we imagine our future?

Example: In the Clean Energy experiments (Gray et al. 2025a,b), communities came together to imagine what the future of energy could look like. By sharing and discussing these ideas, people could question common assumptions and link their own hopes to broader planning efforts

Practical knowledge and know-how:

How do we learn and share practical skills?

Example: In the Efficient Renovations experiments (Foulds et al., 2025b), Knowledge Networks were set up to bring together residents, professionals and community organisations to exchange practical experience around energy-efficient building renovation. Knowledge networks treat renovation as a *social practice*, valuing tacit knowledge, practical know-how, and shared learning across households and communities.

Narratives:

How are changes being talked about?

Example: In the Sustainable Food experiments (Beers et al., 2025), people from different backgrounds worked together using an “arena” approach (Notermans et al., 2022) to shape shared stories about the future of food. These stories linked everyday practices with wider regional and global debates on food production, and supported more sustainable ways forward by strengthening the local and collective initiatives through collaboration, knowledge sharing, and joint action.

Listen here to [a podcast episode](#) with SHARED GREEN DEAL partners about how grassroots movements contribute to food systems transformation.

Business innovation:

How can we make innovation work for everyone?

Example: In the Circular Economy experiments (Ruiz et al. 2025), Local Accelerator Hubs (LAH)* were developed and brought together local businesses, municipalities, and Civil Society Organisations (CSOs) to collectively explore circular business innovations, caring for inclusiveness by engaging vulnerable groups.

*An LAH is an interactive space (physical and virtual) that fosters knowledge-sharing and collaboration between diverse actors.

Strategies:

How do we plan together?

Example: In the Sustainable Mobility experiments (Haufe & Tönkö, 2025), mobility labs were set up in schools as practical spaces for action. These labs helped shape how people think about and use mobility by involving young people, teachers, parents and school administrators in planning, hands-on activities and discussion.

Cultural values:

What does this mean to us?

Example: In the Preserving Biodiversity experiment stream (Šmid Hribar et al., 2025), cultural values are explored and strengthened through Study Circles, in which citizens reconnect to nature and where learning, reflection, and experience help transform how biodiversity is valued.

Fig. 4.1. Bridges to and in the in-between and respective examples from SHARED GREEN DEAL

These bridges exemplified in Figure 4.1 help ideas and learning move in different directions - between people and organisations - spanning multiple levels of action.

What they have in common is that they:

- are created collectively;
- are shaped through interaction and negotiation;
- influence both everyday practices and wider systems.

As ways of working in the *in-between* they are important because they:

- connect people and organisations who would not usually link;
- help translate between different perspectives, languages, and priorities;
- create enough stability for experimentation and learning to take place;
- make informal practices visible and understandable for formal institutions.

Change rarely follows a straight path from small experiments to policy. Instead, it develops through these *in-between spaces*, carried by relationships, shared meanings, practices, and values.

Designing interventions with this in mind means **paying attention to how change moves between people, practices, and institutions** and supporting those connections as part of the process. This toolkit invites to reflect about the *in-between* as the field where change develops and gains traction.

5. The *in-between* in practice: Exercises for action and reflection

This section comprises the following exercises:

- Exercise I - Mapping my / our initiative(s)
- Exercise II - Exploring the *bridges* and potential ripple effects
- Exercise III - Creating a Ripple Effects Map and enhancing intervention strategies

We recommend considering the tips in [Box 2.1](#) as a starting point.

5.1. Exercise I - Mapping my / our initiative

Objective

The first exercise is inspired by constellation work² ([Disterheft, 2021](#); [Macharis 2025](#)) and aims to help visualise and provide clarity about where one's initiative is situated in the conceptual lens of the *in-between*. The exercise invites us to reflect about the dynamics the initiative is embedded in.

What is an initiative and how to decide about one, when multiple could be used?

 By 'initiative', we mean any project, programme, policy, campaign, or organised effort you are involved in.

If you are involved in multiple projects and initiatives, for this exercise we suggest selecting **one** that you are most curious about, or that has some urgency to be understood better. You can, of course, also map several initiatives, if you have the time and motivation to do so.

² Constellations are, among others, a visualisation method for exploring complex systems. By arranging people or objects in space to represent different elements, they make relationships, dynamics, and hidden patterns visible, helping participants gain new insights. Originally developed in systemic practice, the method is increasingly used in research and collaborative learning settings.

ESSENTIALS

🕒 10-30 min.

- Have the *In-between* Map (p. 18) at hand, either as a print out (A4 for individual use, A3 for groups) or draw it similarly on a flipchart sheet.
- Alternative no-paper options are: use ropes as markers on the ground or draw with chalks on the ground (if feasible)
- Large sticky notes, moderation cards or similar
- Pen and reflection sheet with guiding questions (ideally in paper format) or your personal journal

This is an intuitive exercise with no right or wrong placements or answers.

Step 1

Decide on where to do the exercise and prepare accordingly with print-out or alternatives.

Prepare for a reflective moment.
Use a large sticky note or similar to answer:
"My initiative [add name] aims/aimed at ...[add] through ...[add]" (see example on sticky-note)

For groups:

- Think of other elements relevant to your initiative, e.g.
- main actor groups (e.g. young people in our neighbourhood, municipality, parents; adapt to your context);
 - funding bodies,
 - other.

Write each element on a separate sticky note, prepare at least as many as participants are in your group.

Step 2

Example
My initiative **FoodLink** is a **network** that aims to **promote the food transition in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area** by **fostering collaboration** among its approx. 40 members.

Step 3

Place your initiative (or the other elements) on the map. Do this calmly, consciously, intuitively. You may take your time and 'explore' different positions by tuning into your senses and listening to your body wisdom - where does placing your sticky note(s) feel 'right'?

Observe, listen to yourself. Start answering the guiding reflection questions.

Step 4

Step 5 for groups

When everyone in your group is ready, share your observations. Use our prompts to get into the conversation. If you are not familiar with your group, aim for creating a supportive, warm and trustful environment.

Exercise I.a - In-between-Map Sheet

5.2. Exercise II - Exploring the *bridges* and potential ripple effects

Objective

This exercise aims to help gain clarity about the bridges, like community visions, business innovation, knowledge / know-how, strategies, narratives and cultural values (Fig. 4.1), that can be followed in the *in-between* and that help identify possible / potential ripple effects of your initiative.

ESSENTIALS

 10-30 min.

- Reuse from Exercise I: have the *In-between* Map (p. 18) at hand, either as a print out (A4 for individual use, A3 for groups) or draw it similarly on a flipchart sheet.
- Alternative no-paper options are: use ropes as markers on the ground or draw with chalks on the ground (if feasible).
- Print out the 'bridges-cards' (p. 21) and cut them out one by one. For each initiative you should have one set of cards: if you use the exercise in a team meeting involved in the same initiative, one set is enough. If you use them in a workshop with multiple actors groups with several initiatives, prepare one set per group. Some cards are intentionally left blank to be filled with your ideas.
- Large sticky notes, moderation cards or similar
- Pen and reflection sheet with guiding questions (ideally in paper format) or your personal journal

Step 1

Decide on where to do the exercise and prepare accordingly with print-out and/ or alternatives, i.e. the *In-between* Map (p.18) and the 'bridges-cards' (p. 21).

Place the cards in front of you or in the middle of your group so that everyone can see them well.

Step 2

Step 3

Choose one card that represents the approach that feels most relevant for your initiative. If you think more than one card would apply, you can choose more.

Follow the guiding prompts. Experiment with changing perspectives by placing the card(s) in each field of the map - Individuals / In-between / Systems - and answer the guiding questions from the respective perspectives.

Step 4

Exercise II.a - Card Sets Sheet
with Bridges for the In-Between

 Cut along the dashed line

Community visions

*How do we
imagine our
future?*

Business innovation

*How can we make
innovation work
for everyone?*

**Knowledge /
know how**

*How do we learn
and share
practical skills?*

Strategies

*How do we plan
together?*

Narratives

*How are changes
being talked
about?*

Cultural values

*What does this
mean to us?*

Community Visions

*How do we
imagine our
future?*

Business innovation

*How can we make
innovation work
for everyone?*

**Knowledge /
Know how**

*How do we learn
and share
practical skills?*

Strategies

*How do we plan
together?*

Narratives

*How are changes
being talked
about?*

Cultural values

*What does this
mean to us?*

Exercise II.b - Guiding prompts for exploring the *in-between* bridges and potential ripple effects

1. Why do I think this card applies to my / our initiative?

.....

.....

.....

2. Experiment with changing perspectives. In groups, you can divide this reflection depending on the number of participants in your group. E.g., each participant answers one perspective, or if >3 persons, you can form dyads or trios per perspective. Share at the end.

a. How do I answer the question on the card from the Individuals-perspective?

.....

.....

b. How from the Systems-perspective?

.....

.....

c. How from the In-between?

.....

.....

3. Considering your reflection from the previous questions, how can your initiative ripple in the different directions around it? You may think of:

- Who met through this initiative who otherwise would not have connected?
- Which new practices emerged?
- How stable are these practices? What could help stabilize them (even) more?

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Fig. 5.1. Illustrative example on how to change perspectives by placing the card in different areas of the map

5.3. Exercise III - Creating a ripple effects map

Objective

This exercise is inspired by a real-world example from one of the SHARED GREEN DEAL school mobility labs in Ireland (see Box 5.1). The main objective is to explore how ripple effects move across the *in-between* and how they can reveal blind spots, barriers, and enablers for (new) collective action.

Individually or in a group, this exercise invites you to explore how ripple effects move through your initiative and to create a ripple effects map for new insights.

Box 5.1. How ripple effects can reveal blind spots

Learning from school mobility experiments: Seeing what was not initially visible

Within the SHARED GREEN DEAL project, [social experiments on sustainable mobility](#) were carried out through Urban Mobility Labs in schools. These labs brought together young people, parents, teachers, and local stakeholders to co-create and test new approaches to school travel.

The experiments aimed to encourage more sustainable mobility practices, such as cycling to school, while also addressing broader social norms and behaviours related to mobility.

However, through the engagement process, an unexpected dimension emerged.

In one case, girls shared experiences of **gendered harassment while cycling to school**. These experiences had not been visible to adults and were initially described as “unimaginable” ([Aggeli et al. 2025](#), p.23). The discussions also brought forward broader gendered expectations. For example, participants highlighted how girls may feel discouraged from cycling due to norms around appearance and behaviour, such as expectations to remain “clean” or “presentable,” while similar expectations are not placed on boys.

This revealed that:

- mobility is experienced differently depending on gender
- safety is not only about infrastructure, but also about social and cultural dynamics
- norms and expectations (e.g. around appearance and behaviour) can influence mobility practices

This example highlights a **blind spot** in sustainable mobility efforts.

The focus on infrastructure and behaviour did not account for how **gendered experiences in public space** shape everyday mobility. This only became visible through the shared space created by the Urban Mobility Lab.

Recognising such blind spots can:

- deepen understanding of barriers to change
- reveal the role of social norms and lived experiences
- open up new entry points for action

In this sense, ripple effects are not only outcomes of an initiative. They can also act as signals that point towards what has not yet been seen or considered.

ESSENTIALS

🕒 15-40 min.

- Reuse from Exercise I: have the *In-between* Map (p. 18) at hand, either as a print out (A4 for individual use, A3 for groups) or draw it similarly on a flipchart sheet. Alternative no paper options are: use ropes as markers on the ground or draw with chalks on the ground (if feasible)
- Pen(s) and/or markers (ideally in different colours)
- Large sticky notes, moderation cards or similar
- Print out the **Ripple Symbols Sheet** (p. 26) and cut out the symbols (optional). You can also draw them directly on your map.
- Reflection sheet with guiding questions (ideally in paper format) or your personal journal

This is an intuitive and exploratory exercise. There is no right or wrong way to draw ripple effects.

Step 1

Prepare your map

Decide on where to do the exercise and prepare accordingly with print-out and/or alternatives.

Think of one concrete situation / moment, or an outcome like a new practice, new routines etc. that emerged from your initiative.

This could be:

- something that changed;
- something that surprised you;
- feedback from participants;
- a situation where something shifted.

Try to be as specific as possible (e.g. a conversation, behaviour, or event).

Identify it shortly on a sticky note and place it on the map in relation to your initiative: e.g. close, far, leaning towards individuals or towards systems?

Step 2

Step 3

Then ask yourself: *What did this [=what you identified in Step 2] lead to?*

Connect your initiative with this new sticky note, choosing a rippling line or path to show how that what you identified in Step 2 unfolded. Add further elements, thinking for example of potential:

- blindspot(s)
- barrier(s)
- enabler(s)

To better illustrate how this can be done, we used the example of Box 5.1 to exemplify that case (Figure 5.2).

You can do these steps individually or in small groups (3-6 persons). For groups, we recommend using a flipchart sheet, letting the drawing and adding sticky notes unfold. Trust the process. Enjoy creating your map together.

Use the guiding prompts for final reflections (written or verbally).

Step 4

Exercise III.a - Creating a Ripple Effects Map

Guiding prompts for Steps 1-3:

These are supporting questions for your reflection, it is not necessary to answer them all!

- Where did something change?
- Who was affected?
- What happened along the way? How did it happen?
- Where did something slow down, feel difficult, or create tension?
- What is blocking or limiting change here? What is enabling change?
- What became visible here?
- Why had this not been visible before?

Use the symbols on the right for categorizing your elements and draw connections among them.

RIPPLE EFFECT
 BLINDSPOT
 BARRIER
 ENABLERS

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.....

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.....

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Fig. 5.2. Example of a Ripple Effect Map based on the case from the school mobility lab (Box 5.1)

Final reflection prompts for Step 4:

- Where did interactions between people or groups play an important role? Where these
 - moments of exchange,
 - shared learning,
 - collaboration or conflict?
- What did you see that you had not seen before? How did tracing the ripple deepen or change your understanding of your initiative?

Exercise III.b - Ripple Symbols Sheet

Symbols you can use in your map

RIPPLE EFFECT

BLINDSPOT

BARRIER

ENABLERS

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7. Further readings and materials

- Aggeli, A., Wieser, P., Heffernan, R. and Wiedmann, F. (2025). Gender and Intersectional Diversity structures that shape the EU Green Deal. In: Truninger, M.; Disterheft, A.; Carraça, J. (eds). Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16762546>
- Beers, P.J., van Bellen, L., Carraca, J., Girardi, A., Gritti, V., Hebinck, A., Kiewik, J., Mourato, J., Nieboer, S., Silvestri, G., Truninger, M. (2025). Scaling food systems transitions. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15369887>
- Bharucha, Z.P. (2025) Exploring themes of justice, vulnerability and inequality in social innovation processes. In: Truninger, M., Disterheft, A., Carraça, J. (eds). Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16762555>
- Disterheft, A., Pijetlovic, D., & Müller-Christ, G. (2021). On the Road of Discovery with Systemic Exploratory Constellations: Potentials of Online Constellation Exercises about Sustainability Transitions. *Sustainability*, 13(9), Article 9. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13095101>
- Foulds, C., Truninger, M., Aggeli, A., Crowther, A., & Robison, R. (2025a). The Meso Multiple in energy and climate research: How different Social Sciences treat the in-betweenness between the micro and macro. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 119, 103910. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2024.103910>
- Foulds, C., Royston, S., Crowther, A., Aggeli, A., Robison, R., Noreña Ospina, M., Wieser, P. (2025b). Bringing together citizens and professionals to develop know-how for energy efficient renovations. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15270137>
- Gray, E. K., Rohse, M., Fahy, F., Jost, C. (2025a). Community visioning for just, clean energy futures in Europe. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15270128>.
- Gray, E. K., Fahy, F., Kovács, K. (2025b). Governing the European Green Deal Through Local Social Experiments. In: Truninger, M., Disterheft, A., Carraça, J. (eds). Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16762512>
- Haufe, N., Tönkö, A., (2025). Accelerating the transition to sustainable mobility in schools. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15315291>
- Kovács, K., et al., (2024). SHARED GREEN DEAL Case Study Guides. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. Available at: <https://sharedgreendeal.eu/resources/case-study-guides>
- Macharis, C. (2025). Climate Constellations: A Systemic Tool for Exploring Sustainability Transitions. *Systemic Practice and Action Research*, 38(2), 13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11213-025-09722-5>

- Nieboer, S., Hansmeier, H., Beers, P.J., Seus, S., & Hebinck, A. (2025). The Impact of Geographical Enablers and Barriers on the Scaling of Grassroots Innovation Initiatives. In: Truninger, M., Disterheft, A., Carraça, J. (eds). Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16762521>
- Notermans, V.I., von Wirth, T., & Loorbach D. (2022). An experiential guide for Transition Arenas. DRIFT, Erasmus University Rotterdam, Rotterdam, The Netherlands. Available at <https://www.sintef.no/globalassets/project/aces/2022-notermans-et-al-2022-an-experiential-guide-for-transition-arenas.pdf>
- Rasmussen, J. F., Friis-Hansen, E., & Funder, M. (2019). Collaboration between meso-level institutions and communities to facilitate climate change adaptation in Ghana. *Climate and Development*, 11(4), 355–364. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2018.1442797>
- Reid, L., Sutton, P., & Hunter, C. (2010). Theorizing the meso level: The household as a crucible of pro-environmental behaviour. *Progress in Human Geography*, 34(3), 309–327. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309132509346994>
- Ruiz, H., Katusic, V., Hamika S. (2025). Implementing Local Accelerator Hubs to foster business innovation in the circular economy. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15270150>
- Schatzki, T. R. (2012). A Primer on Practices. In J. Higgs, R. Barnett, S. Billett, M. Hutchings, & F. Trede (Eds), *Practice-Based Education: Perspectives and Strategies* (pp. 13–26). SensePublishers. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6209-128-3_2
- Schenk, N. J., Moll, H. C., & Schoot Uiterkamp, A. J. M. (2007). Meso-level analysis, the missing link in energy strategies. *Energy Policy*, 35(3), 1505–1516. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2006.04.013>
- Šmid Hribar, M., Ribeiro, D., Strasser, S., Paliogiannis, H. (2025). Exploring the Study Circle approach in fostering change in biodiversity values among adults. In: Robison, R. and Royston, S. (eds.): Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15270156>
- Truninger, M., Disterheft, A., Carraça, J., Bujeda, J. (2025). Societal challenges and the Green Deal in Europe Post-Coronavirus. In: Truninger, M.; Disterheft, A.; Carraça, J. (eds). Findings and Recommendations of the Secondary Data Analysis of the SHARED GREEN DEAL SSH Priority Themes. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16762528>
- University of Galway (2025). Community Visioning. A Guide to Co-Creating Clean Energy Futures. Cambridge: SHARED GREEN DEAL. Available at: <https://sharedgreendeal.eu/resources/community-visioning-guide-co-creating-clean-energy-futures>

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